

**Learning
Technology
Accelerator**

LEARNING TECHNOLOGY ACCELERATOR
LEA
D1.3 ORDP Data Management Plan
6.2.2019

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Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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1. INTRODUCTION

Scientific data is expensive and time consuming to generate. The gathered data is refined and the results published, but until recent years the raw data has been hidden away from outsiders. The same researchers and their peers in the same institutions have had an upper hand, as they had a lot of raw data to test their hypotheses on before starting a new study. The goal of open access data repositories is that scientists not only publish the results, but also publish the data behind it for others to study and to generate more results. This opens up the scientific research capabilities to everyone everywhere, if someone has already gathered the data needed.

Open access repositories are platforms to store the data. They are free and normally specialized in one field of study. There's a plethora of public open access repositories and it's impossible to single out any recommended ones. Most scientific journals have their recommended repositories. Repositories are normally used through a software that generates the metadata at the same time, but there are sites that take metadata filled by hand. Repositories provide an API (application programming interface) and anyone can make a program to use the repository through the API.

Because there are plenty of repositories and an enormous amount of data, a working search function becomes crucial. The search is implemented through the data about the data, the metadata. Establishing a common vocabulary for the metadata is organized by Project Open Data, which gives the schema for Open data software.

The EU has its own EU Open Data Portal, where all open data published by the EU and its institutions can be accessed. The data generated by the LEA project will also be accessible through this portal. There are no limitations to the data to be stored, other than that the data has to comply to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Attention should be paid to the generation of the metadata, to ensure the searchability of the data. The name of the EU Open Data portal is OpenAIRE and it is the LEA project's data policy to publish research data both in:

The LEA website: <https://www.learntechaccelerator.eu/resources/>

And the OpenAIRE portal: <https://explore.openaire.eu/>

Figure 1: LEA Open Research Data publishing channels

Open access (OA) refers to the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end - user and reusable. 'Scientific' refers to all academic disciplines. In the context of research and innovation, 'scientific information' can mean:

1. peer - reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals) or
2. research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).

This document describes LEA project's Data Management Plan and contains the following sections:

Data Collection
Data Protecting
Data Sharing
LEA Open Research Data Pilot

2. DATA COLLECTING

LEA will contribute to improve and maximize access to and re-use of research data generated by projects as LEA focuses to speed up awareness, dialogue and knowledge transfer. This collaboration will be based upon voluntary participation which is aligned with the Open Innovation approach and LEA will include article 29.3 in our Grant Agreement.

<http://data.europa.eu/euodp/en/data/>

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

In accordance with the Open Innovation approach, to share knowledge and open up innovation systems, LEA will work actively to speed up transfer of knowledge and awareness of innovation procurement in education.

In accordance with EC guidelines of The Open Access (OA), LEA will adopt the following approach of the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) on voluntary participation.

Image 2: How Open Access Works, Horizon2020

The LEA Open research data policy will follow the Horizon2020 Open Access research data guidelines.

Image 3: Horizon2020 Open Access to research data guideline

The two main routes to open access are:

A. Self-archiving / 'green' open access

The author, or a representative, archives (deposits) the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository before, at the same time as, or after publication. Some publishers request that open access be granted only after an embargo period has elapsed.

B. Open access publishing / 'gold' open access

An article is immediately published in open access mode. In this model, the payment of publication costs is shifted away from subscribing readers. The most common business model is based on one-off payments by authors. These costs, often referred to as Article Processing Charges (APCs), are usually borne by the researcher's university or research institute or the agency funding the research. In other cases, the costs of open access publishing are covered by subsidies or other funding models.

In the case of LEA, research data is published openly at the www.learntechaccelerator.eu as well as in the Open Access Repository as part of the Open Research Data Pilot.

3. DATA PROTECTION

The LEA Consortium will follow the legal requirements regarding data protection and ensures, that project members and industry stakeholders, who might participate our schools for LEA School labs work, must understand the legislation governing the use of their products and must therefore carry out any necessary research. This is not only necessary for the testing process, but also to ensure that any innovations prepared during LEA PPI and PCP will be compliant with the General Data

Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the regulations in each country in which it is to be sold.

Potential solutions to be delivered by the service providers will include the collection, recording and processing of personal data from students and teachers. As these data will be processed by automated means, it is in the scope of the GDPR (see Art. 2).

It means that tenderers will have to ensure the observance and compliance with the provisions of the new Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (and demonstrate how they do it). This new regulation was adopted on 27 April 2016 and came into force on 25 May 2018. It applies to all EU member states.

A “controller“ according to the GDPR is “the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data”. In LEA, this role will be fulfilled by the procurers, representing the schools or other authorities, who are responsible to determine the purposes and means of the processing of personal data in the respective country.

A “processor” is “a natural or legal person, public authority or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller”. In LEA, this applies to the suppliers taking part in preparations of future PCP/PPI calls.

The responsibility of the controller is stated in Article 24, where it says: “Taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing as well as the risks of varying likelihood and severity for the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the controller shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and to be

able to demonstrate that processing is performed in accordance with this Regulation. Those measures shall be reviewed and updated where necessary.”

In case of the technologies that are planned to be procured in this project, the controller is not able to fulfill this responsibility on its own. A contract or other legal act, that sets out the details of the processing according to Art. 28 of the GDPR, needs to be concluded between controller and processor. It should specify the subject-matter and duration of the processing, the nature and purpose of the processing, the type of personal data and categories of data subjects and the obligations and rights of the controller.

The processor “makes available to the controller all information necessary to demonstrate compliance with the obligations laid down in this Article and allow for and contribute to audits, including inspections, conducted by the controller or another auditor mandated by the controller.”

Key points of the LEA data protection legislation for the researchers working within the LEA project include:

- Compliance of all delivered services with European and Finnish law (The Finnish partner being the LEA coordinator)
- Data storage within the European Union
- Specification of a privacy declaration to show which data is stored, how the data is stored, who has access to the data, and how the data is used in a record of processing activities (Art. 30)

- Data processing in a manner that ensures confidentiality, accuracy, data minimisation, purpose limitation, fairness and transparency

4. DATA SHARING

The LEA Research data sharing policy is discussed both in the LEA Grant agreement and in the LEA Consortium agreement. The entire LEA dissemination plan is:

- To promote and raise awareness with regard to the project contents and developments – LEARNTECH ACCELERATOR in all aspects as well as PCP and PPI as innovative procurement methods.
- To provide information on the quality, relevance and effectiveness of the results
- To successfully transfer the results to appropriate decision-makers in order to achieve their sustainable promotion and support
- To convince individual end-users to adopt and/or apply the results after the project has ended

The LEA Dissemination plan is described in deliverable D6.1.

The LEA project's domain address:

<https://www.learntechaccelerator.eu>

In the LEA website, research publications can be found under:

<https://www.learntechaccelerator.eu/resources/>

Additionally, research data gathered in the LEA Project will be shared in the open access repository OpenAIRE. The following chapter describes this process as an example and guideline for LEA partners to upload their research content to OpenAIRE.

5. LEA OPEN RESEARCH DATA PILOT

LEA ORDP was conducted for a data set collected in the needs analysis phase in the first 6 months of the Project. The data was gathered by OVGU using LimeSurvey (hosted by OvGU) from students and teachers (over 1000 replies from 7 countries in 7 languages. Example of this data sets questions that can be found in Annex 1 of this document.

5.1 Submitting research data to a local repository

In accordance with the Horizon2020 Open Data guidelines, it was then submitted to a local repository. An easy option is to use “Zenodo” at <https://zenodo.org/>

The screenshot shows the Zenodo.org homepage. At the top, there is a search bar, 'Upload' and 'Communities' buttons, and 'Log in' and 'Sign up' buttons. A maintenance notice is displayed below the header. The main content area features 'Recent uploads' with two entries:

- February 5, 2019 (v1)** Dataset Open Access: **Digital Scholarship services and supports - an overview from Irish Research and National Libraries - Data with Comments**. Authors: Cillian Joy, Eoin Kilfeather, Caleb Derven, Arlene Healy. Description: This dataset contains survey data with comments (cleaned, direct references to institutions removed) and broken down by survey question sections. Some of the data has been converted to counts where it was used to generate the charts. The data is the output of a 2018 CONUL (Ireland's consortium...)
- June 18, 2018 (v1)** Conference paper Open Access: **FabSpace 2.0: Universities Fostering Open Innovation Enabled by Earth Observation and Geo-spatial Information**. Authors: Maranesi, M.; Mothe, J.; Barbier, C.; Islam, M. B.; Turek, A.; Marantos, C. Description: The investments made by the European Commission, the European Space Agency and the Member States in the Earth Observation downstream sector are fostering the development and operationalization of innovative applications and several governmental and industrial customers are progressively adopting...

On the right side, there are three promotional boxes: 'Zenodo now supports usage statistics!', 'Using GitHub?', and 'Zenodo in a nutshell'.

Figure 4: Zenodo.org Open database

Open data portals which are harvested by OpenAIRE can be located from the Openaire portal:

Figures 5-6: European and Finnish Open data portals

Most research institutes and universities have their own portals. In this example the Open Repository of Finland *Etsin* has been is shown. It can be accessed here:

<https://etsin.avointiede.fi/dataset/new>

The answers from LEA's research were anonymized and were put on the servers of Jyväskylä University. *Etsin* is a service offered by the Ministry of Education and Culture of Finland and produced by IT Center for Science (CSC) in Espoo, Finland.

1. Basic information	2. Actors	3. Access information	4. Additional information	5. Identifiers
Dataset title**:	English +	Questionnaire of all LEA School Lab -participants		?
Free description:	English +	Questionnaire from all LEA School Lab participants. How the school labs were carried out, etc		?
Languages*:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This dataset contains non-textual data			?
Keywords*:	x Learntech accelerator x questionnaire			?
Disciplines:	e.g. Mathematics			?

Terms of use: By submitting content, I agree to release this metadata contribution under the [Creative Commons CC0 license](#).

I have asked consent from all persons whose personal information I have added to this descriptive data and informed them of how they can get their personal data removed. Detailed information in: [Terms of use](#)

Check to accept:

Image 3: Finnish Open Data repository *Etsin*

The metadata can be added by hand or through an xml-file that fills everything up. This is handy if the same sort of data is included several

times. The repository has a setup for publishing and the data can be restricted from certain areas or for a certain time. Gathered data itself can be stored to servers or even to a private computer, as there's an option available which requires the interested party to ask for the data from the owner.

5.2 Linking research data to the LEA Project in OpenAIRE

The screenshot shows a web interface for linking a project to OpenAIRE. At the top, it says "Link your project". Below that is a text input field containing "EC | LEARNING TECHNOLOGY ACCELERATOR (LEA)". Underneath the input field, it says "to one or more research results". There is a link "Search for research results" with an information icon. Below the link, there is a search bar with the text "in OpenAIRE" and a dropdown menu showing "Title, doi, author, orcid...". To the right of the search bar is a red "Search" button.

Image 4: Linking the research results to OpenAIRE

After the research data is uploaded to an open repository, it should be linked to the Learning Technology Accelerator Project. The Project can be found in the OpenAIRE portal by searching "European commission" as the funding organisation and with the Grant Agreement number: 779803. After this step, the research data needs to be located e.g. through searching with the title, the author, DOI etc. Then, the link can be made and the publication or research data will be shown on the LEA page in OpenAIRE.

LEA

LEARNING TECHNOLOGY ACCELERATOR (779803)

Project	EC	Open Access mandate for Publications and Research Data
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Funding: H2020 | CSA

Start Date: 2018-03-01

End Date: 2020-02-29

Organization: [EUPK](#) | [INNOVA ESZAK](#) | [VILADECANS](#) | [TORINO](#) | [SBE](#) | [GR](#) | [SERN](#) | [INOVA+](#) | [C.K](#) | [Braga](#) | [RSA](#) | [HSTD](#) | [E.N.T.E.R. GMBH](#) | [JYU](#) | [ICLEI EURO](#) | [UOULU](#) | [OvGU](#)

[Detailed project information \(CORDIS\)](#) →

Publications (0)	+
Research Data (0)	+
Software (0)	+
Other Research Products (0)	+
Statistics	+
Metrics	+

Image 5: LEA in OpenAIRE

After the linking, the research data appears in the Learntech Accelerator page. It is the open data policy of LEA to publish all research data in OpenAIRE as well as on the LEA's own website.

5.3 Lessons learned through LEA Open Research Data Pilot

Data manager perspective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The repository used was easy to browse and the submitted data was relatively easy to browse and
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	<p>search.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The metadata standards are often not filled completely by the person submitting the data (due to lack of time) which make them difficult to find at searches • Open Access data repositories are easy to use and will show their full potential after scientists start to use them more frequently.
<p>Researchers' perspective</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using data gathered for another purpose is difficult if there is no proper labeling and context described. • Gathering research data is the most time-consuming and resource intensive part of a researcher's work, which often means that researchers are reluctant to share their data sets openly. Because of this another competitive researcher might publish the data faster. This is a critical barrier for researchers to share their data sets in open repositories. • The upload process for data is too time-consuming if there is no incentive behind sharing one's data openly. Open science itself is not motivating enough for all researchers.
<p>Project management perspective</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific attention should be paid during the data collection phase to ensure that GDPR regulations are met and that the persons answering the questionnaires/interviews know exactly how their data is managed and published in the future. • IPR of research data gathered during a project should be well defined in the consortium agreement in order to make sure that the whole consortium gets to benefit from the data they gather.

6. Conclusions

This document describes the LEA Data Management Plan. Data collection, protecting and sharing issues guidelines are discussed and it also maps the lessons learned from the LEA Open Research data Pilot. The key barriers to Open data include the researchers not having enough competences in utilising open science repositories as well as the fears of losing their work momentum to competitor publications. In many cases the contexts of the studies conducted do not properly match other researchers' scientific questions and therefore not provide appropriate answers.

Annex 1: List of Survey Questions (Teacher)

QID¹	Full text
01	Are you a teacher or a student?
02	In which country do you work?
03	Please enter your gender.
04	Please indicate the type of school you are teaching at. ²
05	Specify what changes you expect in your lessons through the use of learning software.
06	Specify how often the computer/laptop or mobile devices are used in class each week.
061	Please indicate in which subjects the computer/laptop or mobile devices are used
07	Specify the types of teaching materials you prefer to use.
08	Which circumstances prevent the successful use of learning software / learning management systems in the classroom?
09	Please select the points that would support you in the use of learning software.
10	Are there special information events or training hours for the introduction of learning software / learning management systems for teachers?
11	Should there be special information events or training hours for the introduction of learning software / learning management systems for teachers?

¹ QID - Question Identifier

² Question different depending on chosen country (QID 02)

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12	Please select the skills you think you need to master in order to use learning software in your lessons.
13	Please assess your skills in working with the computer.
14	Are there special information events or training hours for the introduction of learning software/ learning management systems for students?
15	Should there be special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software/ learning management systems for students?
16	Select the points you identify as barriers for students to learn successfully with learning software/ learning management systems.
17	Specify what skills students need to demonstrate to successfully participate in lessons with learning software/ learning management systems.
18	How important are the following computer skills for students to use learning software?
19	Please indicate the technical equipment your school is equipped with.
20	Please indicate which classroom equipment you need for the use of learning software.
21	Please indicate which type of equipment you prefer.

